

SCOLIOSIS: A COMMON PROBLEM AMONG CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract. *One of the most frequent diseases of the musculoskeletal system in school-age children are posture disorders and scoliosis. Early detection of the symptoms of the disease increases the effectiveness of its treatment. Paying attention to all factors affecting children's health and creating comfortable conditions for them takes the main place in their physiological development.*

Keywords: *musculoskeletal system, posture disorder, scoliosis, lordosis, kyphosis, asymmetric development, spine.*

Relevance of the problem: Physical development is a complex concept reflecting anthropometric status [1]. “Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease and physical defects”. This definition is given in the preamble to the constitution of the World Health Organization, adopted at the International Health Conference in New York, June 19-22, 1946. The document was signed on July 22, 1946, by representatives of 61 countries and entered into force on April 7, 1948. The definition has not been changed since then [2].

The life of any organism is adaptive in nature. Already at the stage of the first year of life, the formation of such necessary curves as lordosis and kyphosis are manifested in the deviation of the spine to the front and back, respectively. They appear as a person grows and acquires certain skills. In the case of uneven loads on the musculoskeletal framework, joint and ligamentous apparatus and discs, there are deviations of the spine in the form of bends to one side or the other from the vertical axis. Thus, one of the most common diseases of the musculoskeletal system - posture disorders and scoliosis - develops [3, 4].

Posture is the habitual posture of a person at rest or in motion. It is determined by the position of the pelvis, curvature of the spine, position of the head relative to the body, and muscle tension. The bone system and ligaments are passive, whereas muscles are an active element of the musculoskeletal system [5, 6, 7].

Human posture begins to form from the moment of birth. The key role in its development is played by the spine, which has physiological curves. At the early stage of life, a child has necessary physiological curvatures such as lordosis and kyphosis. These changes manifest themselves in the forward and backward deviation of the spine, respectively. They arise as a result of growth and acquisition of certain motor skills by a person [3, 4, 8, 9].

Often children have posture disorders under the influence of various factors, which can negatively affect the development of the body.

Factors that negatively affect the formation of posture include:

- Poor skeletal muscle development;
- Lack of physical activity;
- Visual defects, nasopharyngeal and hearing disorders;

- Frequent infectious diseases;
- Use of soft beds (cots);
- Use of desks and tables that do not correspond to the child's height;
- Inadequate rest;
- The child's imitation of friends or relatives who have incorrect posture [9, 10].

According to research, posture disorders occur during the period of the most rapid growth of a child: at the ages of 5-8 years and 11-12 years. This period can be called the time of basic posture development, as it is during this time that bones and muscles are growing at an accelerated rate, and posture maintenance mechanisms are not yet fully adapted to these changes. During this period, children with underdeveloped muscular systems often experience prolonged performance of tasks such as reading or writing, which requires maintaining the same posture for long periods of time. Because of the muscle weakness, the child often “bends” his back, his body tilts to the left or right, and his neck stretches forward. When performing writing tasks, the child lies down on the surface of the desk and tilts his or her head. This position increases the risk of not only posture disorders, but also the development of myopia by 2-5 times [11, 12].

Due to overstrain of the musculoskeletal system, the spine deviates from the vertical axis to one side or another. As a result, one of the most common diseases of the musculoskeletal system - scoliosis - develops [3, 4].

Scoliosis (from Greek “skoliosis” - curvature) is a lateral curvature of the human spine [7, 8, 13, 14]. If we pay attention to the history of posture disorders, the prevalence of pediatric scoliosis before the October Revolution in 1917 was 29%, and in 1921 among schoolchildren in Moscow and Leningrad - 38%. As a result of preventive measures in the pre-war years, the incidence of scoliosis decreased to 27%. After 1945, scoliosis was detected in 82.1% of children who endured the blockade of Leningrad. In 1991, it was found in 32% of the studied adolescents [11].

General statistics show that more than 40% of the world's population suffers from scoliosis, with 10% of patients requiring treatment. This disease is especially prevalent among school-aged children [15]. According to the data, girls are less likely to have spinal curvature than boys. It is also 2-5 times less common in high school students than in elementary school students who spend a lot of time at a desk. Among children who walk to school, the disease is 3-4 times less common than in those who arrive by car [5, 14].

A distinction is made between congenital and acquired types of scoliosis.

Causes of congenital scoliosis:

- Underdevelopment of the spine;
- Abnormally formed extra vertebrae;
- Endocrine system disorders during fetal development.

Causes of acquired scoliosis:

- Trauma to the spine;
- Bony protrusion in the cervical spine;
- Prolonged exposure of the body to uncomfortable and unnatural positions;
- Asymmetrical development of muscle mass;
- Improper or impaired physical development;
- Excessive physical activity or lack thereof [3, 8, 11, 16, 17].

Additional factors contributing to the development of scoliosis include:

Improperly arranged desks in school classrooms (students must sit for their height);

School bags that are inappropriate for the child's age;

Holding a child with one hand while walking, etc. [13, 18, 19].

Symptoms of scoliosis: The symptoms of the disease usually depend on its degree.

By origin, scoliosis is divided into:

-Myopathic,

-Neurogenic,

-Dysplastic,

-Rubic,

-Traumatic,

-Idiopathic.

According to the shape of curvature:

C-shaped scoliosis (with one arc of curvature),

S-shaped scoliosis (with two arcs of curvature),

Z-shaped scoliosis (with three curvature arcs) [17, 20].

Primary signs of scoliosis and posture disorders:

Distorted posture,

Asymmetrical position of shoulders and shoulder blades,

A feeling of discomfort in the spine,

Weakness of the back muscles,

Head and spine pain [21, 22].

When the spine is curved, its mobility decreases and the shape of the thorax changes.

Patients complain of intercostal and muscular pain [23].

Severe curvatures of the spine and thorax significantly affect the functions of internal organs:

-Decrease the volume of pleural cavities,

-Disrupt respiratory mechanics,

-Deteriorate the function of external respiration,

-Decrease arterial blood oxygen saturation,

-Change the character of tissue respiration,

-Cause hypertension in the small circulation,

-Cause myocardial hypertrophy in the right side of the heart [7, 13, 24].

Treatment of scoliosis: Scoliosis is treated conservatively and surgically.

Conservative methods include:

-Chenault braces,

-Specialized exercises such as SEAS.

Studies have shown that only a corrective corset can stop the progression of the disease.

LFK is used in slowly developing forms of scoliosis. It is important to remember! Massage, manual therapy, osteopathy and physiotherapy are not treatments for scoliosis.

The goals of conservative treatment are to:

-Stop the progression of scoliosis,

-Correct the deformity,

-Preserve correct posture.

Scoliosis treatment methods depend on the type of the disease and the degree of spinal deformity. In posture disorders and scoliosis, the child should be under the supervision of an orthopedist until bone growth is complete.

Treatment can be carried out on an outpatient basis, in sanatoriums or in orthopedic hospitals.

Surgical methods of treatment are used in severe forms of scoliosis and include surgery to attach metal rods to the spine. This method is considered the most effective for severe curvatures [10, 25].

Another method of treatment is swimming, which helps to solve the following problems:

- Rectification of the spine,
- Correction of deformity,
- Teaching correct posture,
- Improving coordination of movements,
- Enhancement of muscle tone,
- Correction of flat feet,
- Formation of correct breathing,
- Improving the functions of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems,
- Learning swimming skills [25, 26].

Prevention:

Schools and kindergartens regularly conduct medical examinations to detect scoliosis and other diseases of the musculoskeletal system. The presence of spinal curvature, flat feet is checked, and diagnostic procedures such as CT scans, screening tests and X-rays are performed [10, 25].

In conclusion, the prevention of scoliosis in children should be started from the first days of life. The main tasks include early detection of posture disorders, monitoring of the child's gait and sitting posture, as well as proper selection of furniture (desks) for height and appropriate school bags.

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